

HCN Distribution in Planet-forming Disks

DEVIN SULLIVAN, KARIN I. ÖBERG, CHARLES J. LAW

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ABSTRACT

The organic molecule HCN is found throughout the Universe and has been identified as a key ingredient to the prebiotic chemistry that lead to the development of life on Earth. HCN has been shown to be necessary for the production of amino acids and for this reason it is of interest whether it might be abundant on planets outside of our solar system. Mapping HCN in planet-forming regions allows us to better understand the prevalence of systems where this key component to life might be available. In this report we use observational data at millimeter wavelengths from the Atacama Large Millimeter/Submillimeter Array of nearby young stars accompanied by protoplanetary disks – structures of gas and dust that are the predecessors of planets – to constrain the properties of HCN in these systems. In particular, we analyze two rotational emission lines from HCN for 3 different systems to make use of rotational diagram analyses to constrain the column density and rotational temperature of the molecule in the protoplanetary disks.

For the AS 209 system we report a column density of $1.7(\pm 0.5) \times 10^{13} \text{cm}^{-2}$ and a rotational temperature of $11 \pm 2 \text{K}$. For the disk MWC 480 we find values of $1.4(\pm 0.3) \times 10^{13} \text{cm}^{-2}$ and $10 \pm 1 \text{K}$ for the same parameters and in the disk GM Aur $5.5(\pm 1.8) \times 10^{12} \text{cm}^{-2}$ and $21 \pm 7 \text{K}$. These results are consistent with each other and seem to suggest that disks around various star types may all harbor HCN under similar conditions, but this requires more evidence. These results mark important first constraints on the column density and rotational temperatures of the HCN in AS 209 and GM Aur, and are complementary to existing values for MWC 480. These are promising for further analysis to understanding the presence of this molecule critical to the development of life.

1. INTRODUCTION

Protoplanetary disks are disk-shaped regions of gas and dust surrounding a young star. These disks precede the planetary formation process - in fact, the disk not only constitutes the material which will accrete into planets and comets, but actively plays a role in the formation processes. The Atacama Large Millimeter/Submillimeter Array (ALMA) is well-suited for the study of the chemistry of these regions as it can resolve AU-scale images and measure the line intensity for the rotational emission lines of some key molecules present in the disk (Bergin & Cleeves 2018). It is important to understand these planet-forming disks as a part of the evolutionary history of planetary systems.

Radiation both internal and external is responsible for the active gas-phase chemistry observed in protoplanetary disks. The star produces UV and X-ray radiation which is dominant at shorter distances while external sources provide UV radiation (as well as X-ray and galactic cosmic rays) which primarily effects regions closer to the surface of the disk. This results in gas temperatures decreasing as distance from the surface of the

disk increases until you reach the cold midplane region. Gas temperature also decreases as a function of radius as stellar radiation has smaller effects over further distances (Bergin & Cleeves 2018). The structure of the disk flares out as the distance from the star increases. As a result of the height of the disk increases as a function of radius, the vertical temperature gradient is much less dramatic further along the radius of the disk (Walsh et al. 2010). Models agree in the expectation that HCN is located as a part of the "warm molecular layer" protected from photodissociation near the surface of the disk and freeze out at the cold midplane (Walsh et al. 2010, Aikawa et al. 2002).

Hydrogen cyanide, HCN, is an incredibly important molecule for study in these systems because of the integral role it plays in the origin of life (Patel et al. 2015). They find that HCN is the key molecule to the development of ribonucleotides, amino acids, and lipids. This molecule's presence on a young Earth was crucial to the development of life as we know it, so we find it compelling to search for the conditions under which we can find it in the planet-forming disks around young stars in our galaxy as it tells us more generally about one spe-

cific step in the conditions for the origins of life in our universe. The molecules in the protoplanetary disk may be available to the planets and comets that form over time - suggesting that this is a good place to check for an important condition for life as we know it.

The purpose of this project is to put initial constraints on the rotational temperature and column density of HCN in the sample of disks. We then hope to compare the conditions of HCN across the variety of stars included in the sample to see if there is an explicit difference depending upon the mass, luminosity, or other properties of the star or if HCN is found in similar conditions in all disks. We also compare our findings to existing chemical models to test their quality. In section 2 we introduce the sources included in our analysis. In section 3 we describe the methodology of observations, data reduction, and rotational diagram analysis. We then present our results in section 4 followed by a discussion of their implications in section 5.

2. SOURCE SAMPLE

The sources selected for this project were part of a large program to try to better understand the chemical composition and structures of protoplanetary disks more generally. These sources are all at an optimal inclination for observation of both radial and vertical features ($\sim 45^\circ$), and are nearby young stars with circumstellar disks that have been previously observed to have active chemistry and a variety of dust feature in their disks. As a part of this project, we analyze three of the five targets of the large program. Included in the observation proposal are two more disks, HD 163296 and Im Lup. Unfortunately, the datasets for these sources were not ready to be used within the timeline of this project. The potential to extend the scope of this project beyond the three disks analyzed here is an exciting opportunity to continue to shed light on HCN in protoplanetary disks.

AS 209 is a T Tauri type star, a pre-main sequence star of spectral type K5. It is nearby at a distance of 126 pc, a necessity for the sensitivity required to observe the millimeter wavelength emissions of HCN. It has narrow nested dust ring structure that makes it a compelling target for the program to see potential impacts of dust structures on the chemical distributions in the disk, as well as several gaps in ^{12}CO emission, possibly indicating the presence of a planet already forming in the young star's disk (Guzmán et al. 2018). GM Aur is also a nearby K5 type star. It has not only 2 prominent rings of dust, but also a large inner cavity (Macías et al 2018.). MWC 480 is a Herbig Ae type star, another type of pre-main sequence star, but it is a hotter source, with spectral type A4. It exhibits a potentially forming

planet (Liu et al. 2019). In the discussion we will investigate whether spectral type and structure might have an impact on our findings.

3. METHODS

3.1. Observations

Each source was observed at frequencies of 90 and 260 GHz, corresponding to the J=1-0 and J=3-2 rotational lines of HCN, respectively. The observational work was not a part of my work on this project and is part of a larger group collaboration studying astrochemical properties of protoplanetary disks. The data sets were calibrated and continuum subtracted by the group and was also not a part of my work for this project.

3.2. Data Reduction

Using CASA¹ software, the relevant spectral windows were split into a new data set which was then imaged using the `tclean` function with channel widths of 0.21 km/s for the 1-0 transition and 0.41 km/s for the 3-2 transition using a Briggs robust weighting parameter of 0.5. The data were cleaned to a threshold of 3x the rms baseline noise. Finally, we correct for the primary beam to produce our channel maps, reported in the figures at the conclusion of the paper.

We first analyze the spectra for each rotational emission line. We visually identify the structure of each emission line - which is particularly important for the 1-0 transition where we see 3 fine structure lines which overlap and bleed into each other for each source. The 3-2 transition has a much more simple structure, a bimodal peak created by the rotational velocity of the disk. Additionally, we produce moment 0 maps for the 1-0 and 3-2 transition of each source. These are created by integrating over each channel with signal, and we include these as well.

3.3. Rotational Diagram Analysis

Table 1. Source Sample

Source	Star	d	i
		(pc)	($^\circ$)
AS 209	K5	126	38
GM Aur	K5	140	49
MWC 480	A4	142	37

¹ McMullin et al. 2007

One of the primary goals of this paper is to constrain the column density and rotational temperature of HCN in the disks we observed. As such, we employ a rotational diagram analysis to evaluate the disk-averaged column density and the rotational temperature of HCN in each disk (Goldsmith & Langer 1999).

To perform this analysis integrated flux density is calculated from the spectral emission for each transition by integrating the area beneath the curve and converting to units of K km/s (these values are reported in the Integrated Line Intensity table). Following the analysis done in *Law et al. 2018*, upper level column density can be related to the integrated by the equation:

$$\frac{N_u}{g_u} = \frac{3k_B \int T_{mb} dV}{8\pi^3 \nu S \mu^2} \quad (1)$$

Here N_u is the upper level column density, g_u is the statistical weighting of the upper level, k_B is the Boltzmann constant, $\int T_{mb} dV$ is the integrated flux density, ν is the central frequency of the transition, μ is the dipole moment and S is the line strength (both μ and S are obtained from the Cologne Database of Molecular Spectroscopy (CDMS ² catalog of Splatalogue).

Table 2. HCN Line Properties^a

Transition	Frequency (MHz)	E_u (K)	$S_{ij}\mu^2$ (D ²)
1-0	88631.60	4.25362	26.82171
3-2	265886.43	25.52119	80.45866

^aAll line property values are from Splatalogue's CDMS Catalog

Table 3. Integrated Line Intensities

Source	Transition	Int. Flux Density	RMS
		K km/s	K km/s
AS 209	1-0	10.4087	2.30603
AS 209	3-2	13.0476	1.68363
MWC 480	1-0	8.7049	1.14581
MWC 480	3-2	9.4000	1.22793
GM Aur	1-0	2.1015	0.53464
GM Aur	3-2	6.8551	0.83895

² <http://www.astro.uni-koeln.de/cdms/catalog>

Making the assumptions that the molecule is in local thermal equilibrium (LTE) and that emission lines are optically-thin, we can relate obtain values for the rotational temperature, T_{rot} , and total column density, N_{tot} , by the relation:

$$\frac{N_u}{g_u} = \frac{N_{tot}}{Q(T_{rot})} e^{-\frac{E_u}{T_{rot}}} \quad (2)$$

$Q(T_{rot})$ is the partition function for HCN and E_u is the upper level energy (the values for which we get from the CDMS catalogue).

$\frac{N_u}{g_u}$ was then semi-log plotted against the upper state energy E_u , so that the line of best fit could be used to determine values for N_{tot} and T_{rot} . The results of the rotational diagram analysis are reported in Table 4 and the diagrams are included as Figures 2-4. We account for an inherent 10% calibration uncertainty contributing to error throughout as well as an average of the noise of the spectral baseline. These error measures are included as our errorbars in the rotational diagrams and we report all column densities and rotational temperatures with 1σ uncertainty.

4. RESULTS

With our reduced data we produce channel maps for each observed transition of HCN in each system. This is the image at separate velocity channels, or images from specific frequencies centered around the central peak of the emission line. These illustrate the disks' rotations - the emission line is Doppler shifted with the differential rotation of each disk. We additionally include moment 0 maps, for each observed transition from each source. These are images produced by integrating over the total intensity of each velocity. Here we can see how the intensity of the emission line over the entirety of the source. Finally, we plot the flux density for each emission line as a function of radio velocity, this could alternatively be represented as a function of frequency or wavelength. In each of these plots we identify hyperfine emission features of the J=1-0 transition. We shade the region over which we integrated to measure the integrated flux density for use in our rotational diagram analysis (these

Table 4. Rotational Analysis Results

Source	Rotational Temperature	Column Density
	(K)	(cm ⁻²)
AS 209	11 ± 2	1.7(±.5) × 10 ¹³
MWC 480	10 ± 1	1.4(±.3) × 10 ¹³
GM Aur	21 ± 7	5.5(±1.8) × 10 ¹²

Figure 1. Spectral emission from AS 209. Note that the emission signal is much larger from the 3-2 transition but is divided by 10 and offset by 60 mJy to show features on the same plot. The shaded region is the region over which we integrate to get the integrated flux density.

Figure 2. Rotational diagram for HCN in AS 209. Included are the resulting values for column density and rotational temperature.

values are reported in Table 3). All channel maps, moment 0 maps, and spectra are reported at the conclusion of the paper.

As a result of our rotational diagram analysis, we derive column densities of $1.7(\pm.5) \times 10^{13} \text{cm}^{-2}$, $1.4(\pm.3) \times 10^{13} \text{cm}^{-2}$, and $5.5(\pm 1.8) \times 10^{12} \text{cm}^{-2}$ for the HCN in the

Figure 3. Rotational diagram for HCN in MWC 480. Included are the resulting values for column density and rotational temperature.

circumstellar disk of AS 209, MWC 480, and GM Aur respectively. We also report derived rotational temperatures of $11 \pm 2 \text{K}$, $10 \pm 1 \text{K}$, and $21 \pm 7 \text{K}$ for the same systems.

5. DISCUSSION

Figure 4. Rotational diagram for HCN in GM Aur. Included are the resulting values for column density and rotational temperature.

These are important first results for rotational temperature and column density of HCN in the disks of AS 209 and GM Aur and are interesting to compare to existing values for MWC 480. *Chapillon et al. 2012* found a column density of $1.1 \times 10^{12} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ for HCN in MWC 480, which is an order of magnitude of lower than our result. They observed the J=1-0 emission line, and fit the measured integrated intensity to a chemical model for the disk. The signal they measure is noisier than ours and their modeling of the disk could be the result in the discrepancy. *Chapillon et al. 2012a* didn't directly try to derive the value for the rotational temperature of HCN in MWC 480, but rather they adopted a value of 30 K for a model based off the close similarities between the rotational temperatures of CN, which they measured in several Herbig Ae stars, and HCN. These discrepancies also could be a result of assumptions made in my analysis. It is worth noting that this is a relatively simple analysis where we assume that emission is optically thin and that the molecule is emitting from a region at LTE, this could perhaps be a reason for the difference between my findings and those in literature.

Upon comparing the small sample of disks analyzed we can make a few inferences. The rotational temperature are consistently low, indicating that the temperature region HCN is located in generally is lower than that used in models such as those of *Chapillon et al. 2012a*. This finding could improve these existing models. Additionally, it appears as though there is no clear trend in either column density or rotational temperature based on star type, indicating that other factors might dominate these parameters.

Other improvements can also be made to the observations and analysis carried out in this project. A review of existing measurements of the rotational temperatures and column densities of HCN in other disks that have

already been studied along with analysis of the two remaining disks in the project proposal could lead us to more concrete conclusions based on trends we observe, something that was outside the scope of this project. A more statistically rigorous argument could be made to start describing how HCN is distributed in protoplanetary disks more generally. Improved resolution would permit us to radially resolve the column density at different distances out from the star, and interesting result to compare to the modeled column densities of *Walsh et al. 2010*, which outlines several different models of column density at various radii.

The constraint on the temperature region only tells us part of the full picture of where HCN lies in the disk. To actually constrain its physical location we need to measure the actual temperature structure of the disk and understand the turbulence within the disk - which is responsible for spreading these molecules to different vertical levels.

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Figure 5. Moment 0 images of AS 209. On the left is the 1-0 transition and on the right is the 3-2 transition. X-axis and Y-axis show the source in right ascension (J200) and declination (2000) with the color bar depicting relative intensity.

Figure 6. Spectral emission from MWC 480. Note that the emission signal is much larger from the 3-2 transition but is divided by 10 and offset by 60 mJy to show features on the same plot. The shaded region is the region over which we integrate to get the integrated flux density.

Figure 7. Moment 0 images of MWC 480. On the left is the 1-0 transition and on the right is the 3-2 transition. X-axis and Y-axis show the source in right ascension (J200) and declination (2000) with the color bar depicting relative intensity.

Figure 8. Spectral emission from GM Aur. Note that the emission signal is much larger from the 3-2 transition but is divided by 10 and offset by 60 mJy to show features on the same plot. The shaded region is the region over which we integrate to get the integrated flux density.

Figure 9. Moment 0 images of GM Aur. On the left is the 1-0 transition and on the right is the 3-2 transition. X-axis and Y-axis show the source in right ascension (J200) and declination (2000) with the color bar depicting relative intensity.

Figure 10. Channel maps for the 1-0 transition in AS 209.

Figure 11. Channel maps for the 3-2 transition in AS 209.

Figure 12. Channel maps for the 1-0 transition in MWC 480.

Figure 13. Channel maps for the 3-2 transition in MWC 480.

Figure 14. Channel maps for the 1-0 transition in GM Aur.

Figure 15. Channel maps for the 3-2 transition in GM Aur.